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The conference will be organized in a HYBRID way, which will allow for both physical and online participation of the attendees.

The global economy of the twenty-first century has transformed the economic, social, and political landscape in a profound way. This century has been the scene of revolutions in information and communication technologies, enhanced economic integrations with capital mobility across readers, and a rapidly changing social environment.

In this context, **IRCOBESS 2024**'s main theme is “*New Approaches in Economics and Business: Problems & Opportunities*”. In accordance with this, we welcome studies in the fields of economics and business management; also, in branches of social sciences such as public administration, politics, regional studies, and international studies that are related to economics and business management. Studies that are not within the scope of the conference will not be evaluated.

The aim of the conference is to gather leading academicians, policymakers, independent scholars, and researchers to share their knowledge, and new ideas as well as to discuss future development in these fields. It also provides a premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners, and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Economics, Business, and Social Sciences.

An additional goal of the **IRCOBESS 2024** is to offer an opportunity for young researchers, academicians, and practitioners with multidisciplinary interests to meet and interact with members inside and outside their own particular disciplines.

LEGAL SUPPORT FOR THE SIMPLIFICATION OF CUSTOMS CONTROLS: A MODERN NECESSITY

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ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the analysis of the role of legal norms in the process of simplification of customs control, which has become an essential condition for the effective development of foreign trade in the context of globalisation. International standards such as the Kyoto Convention and the Trade Facilitation Agreement (TFA) are examined as a basis for creating a legal framework that facilitates the reduction of administrative barriers and the simplification of procedures related to the movement of goods across borders..

KEY WORDS

Customs Control, Legal Norms, Trade Facilitation, International Standards, Kyoto Convention, Trade Facilitation Agreement (TFA), Administrative Barriers Border Procedures, Simplification of Customs Procedures, Globalization, Customs Regulations.

INTRODUCTION

In our Republic, great attention is paid to the promotion of foreign trade, simplification of customs procedures, incentives and preferences for participants in foreign economic activities, and elimination of existing administrative and technical barriers.

A number of targeted measures are being implemented within the customs authorities to create a legal framework for the simplification of customs control. In particular, the resumption of Uzbekistan's accession process to the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2019 and the ratification of the Kyoto Convention on 21 December 2020 [1] were important steps towards aligning the country's customs procedures with international standards.

Despite the numerous reforms carried out in this area, Uzbekistan remains one of the few countries that are not members of the WTO. This situation requires further simplification of customs control, examination of its theoretical and legal aspects, improvement of the quality of regulatory legal acts and ensuring their scientific justification, reliability, objectivity and analytical rigour.

The modern legal definition of customs control in most WTO member countries is based on the concept outlined in the Kyoto Convention on the Simplification and Harmonisation of Customs Procedures (Kyoto, 1973) [2]. According to Standard E7./F3 of the General Annex to the Convention, customs control is defined as a set of measures applied by customs authorities to ensure compliance with customs legislation.

Control during clearance: This includes

Documentary examination: Examination of documents for conformity and accuracy.

Customs inspection: Physical examination of goods.

Goods identification: Ensuring that declared and actual goods match.

Personal inspection: Examination of individuals where necessary.

Post clearance control: This involves

Customs audit: Verifying compliance by examining transactions and documentation after clearance.

Systematic audit of traders: Comprehensive assessment of traders' compliance with customs requirements. (Figure 1.1.)

Figure 1.1. Stages and forms of customs control according to the Kyoto Convention:

According to E.G. Bormotova and N.G. Lipatova, in the international practice of customs clearance and control, taking into account the "Framework Standards of Security and Facilitation of Global Trade", a three-stage structure of customs operations has been formed: prior notification, declaration and payment of customs duties [3].

In accordance with the "Framework Standards of Security and Facilitation of Global Trade" of the World Customs Organisation (WCO) [4] and Standard 6.1 of the Kyoto Convention, it is stipulated that all goods imported into and exported from customs territories, including vehicles, are subject to customs control.

S.A. Agamagomedova, one of the leading scholars of the Eurasian Economic Union, notes that customs control is a crucial tool of state regulation in this area. It rests on three main "pillars": the risk management system (RMS), audits and the development of information technologies [5].

Today, the main task is to strengthen the purchasing power of the population and to meet the demand for essential food and consumer goods. According to Chapter 6, Article 6.2 of the Annex to the International Convention on the Simplification and Harmonisation of Customs Procedures, "customs control shall be minimized to the extent necessary to ensure compliance with customs legislation".

Article 272 of the Customs Code defines the procedure for releasing goods before the customs declaration is submitted.

On the basis of this article, goods specified in Article 251 of the Code may be released when crossing the customs border prior to submitting a customs declaration or completing customs operations, provided that the conditions specified in this article are met by the declarant or customs broker.

From the above, it can be concluded that under the conditions provided for in Article 272 of the Customs Code, it is not necessary to deliver the goods to the customs warehouse and the customs clearance of these goods is carried out in accordance with the established requirements.

In recent years, reforms in customs administration, simplification of trade procedures, removal of bureaucratic barriers and abolition of more than ten permits have laid the foundation for bringing customs procedures in line with international standards. The movement of goods across customs borders is a complex, multi-step process. Modern customs legislation requires not only its integration and adaptation to unified international standards, but also its simplification where possible.

In our country, a legislative framework has been established for the organization and improvement of customs audits. A number of regulatory legal acts have been adopted to implement international norms and standards into national legislation. Article 7.5 of the WTO Trade Facilitation Agreement [6] states that "WTO Members shall fulfil the requirements for the introduction of customs audits to improve their customs administration". In addition, Article 6.6 of the International Convention on Simplification and Harmonisation of Customs Procedures states that "Customs control systems shall include audit-based controls".

Based on these provisions and in accordance with the amendments made to the Customs Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-748 dated 1 February 2022, a new provision was added to Article 201 entitled "Customs control after release of goods".

According to this provision, if customs authorities have sufficient and confirmed grounds for suspecting violations of customs legislation, they have the right to conduct customs control, including through customs audit methods.

This procedure for conducting customs audits is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in 2021 the Cabinet Resolution ¹ 101 "On the Procedure for Conducting Customs Audits" was adopted.

In view of the above, this scientific study takes into account the fact that customs control is a constantly developing process. It is necessary to create conditions for foreign trade participants on the one hand, and to ensure a "golden balance" between the fulfilment of international agreements and the protection of the economic security and fiscal functions of the state on the other. On this basis, scientific proposals and practical recommendations have been developed.

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